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SIMULATION OF FIBER ORIENTATION DURING COMPRESSION MOLDING PROCESS OF CF RTP-SMC

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OUTLINE

- **Background**
 - ✓ Background of the topic
 - ✓ Purpose and Approach
- **Experimental Fabrication with different flow circumstances**
- **Mechanical test & Internal structure characterization**
 - ✓ Three-point bending test and result
 - ✓ Fiber orientation distribution analysis
- **Numerical simulation**
 - ✓ Method
 - ✓ Molding simulation and result
- **Correlation and tasks**

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- Environmental issues - Global Warming

Anomalies are deviation from baseline (1981-2010 Average).
 The black thin line indicates surface temperature anomaly of each year.
 The blue line indicates their 5-year running mean.
 The red line indicates the long-term linear trend.

• CFRP & CFRTTP & Sheet Molding Compound (SMC) (CTT)

Type of composite system	Injection molded	Mat structure thermoplastics	Chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) Sheet Molding Compound	Continuous Laminates
Fiber volume fraction V_f	Relatively low	Middle (20-30%)	High (>50%)	High (>50%)
Aspect ratio L/D	Low (variation)	Middle (hundreds)	High (hundreds-thousands)	Highest
Formability	Superior	General	Superior	Directional dependent
In-plane isotropy	Process dependent	Feasible	Feasible	Designable

Propose and verify a reliable CFRTTP-SMC compression molding simulation method

Simulate complex component forming process in industry

- Process simulation on SMCs

Direct Simulation Models at Microscale and Mesoscale	Abaqus	ABAQUS/EXPLICIT(SPH) ABAQUS/EXPLICIT (Coupled Lagrangian Eulerian (CEL) feature.)
	3D TIMON	3D TIMON CompositePRESS
Macroscopic Process Simulation	Moldflow	
	Moldex3D(+LS-Dyna)	

Verification on:

Fiber orientation; Compression force; Flow front curves; Modulus distribution; Warpage; Fiber length; thickness

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Chopped CF RTP-SMC sheet with PA6

Cut sheet in Mold

Before molding

Molding condition

Temperatures/°C	270
Force/kN	156
Time/min	20

$$\text{Charge ratio} = \frac{\text{Area after molding}}{\text{Area before molding}}$$

Area after molding is constant
Area before molding is used to control the charge ratio

Expected parameter of different charge ratio plate:

Size of sheet	Charge Ratio	Weight/g	Thickness/mm
125x250 (Size of the mold)	1	92	2
125x167	1.5	92	2
125x125	2	92	2
125x100	2.5	92	2

(2 plate for each size, totally 8 plates)

N°	Temperatures setpoint			Force setpoints		Duration	
	Gradient (°C/mm)	Upper platen (°C)	Lower platen (°C)	Gradient (kN/s)	Force (kN)	(mm : s)	
1	20.0	270	270	2.0	16	20	0
2	20.0	270	270	2.0	0	0	3
3	20.0	270	270	2.0	156	10	0
4	20.0	20	20	2.0	156	10	0
5	0.0	0	0	0.0	0	0	0

After molding

E.g. Molded plate of Charge ratio 1.5

Charge Ratio: 1

Charge Ratio: 2.5

- CFRTP-SMC sheets in the mold before molding of different charge ratio:

Charge Ratio: 1

Charge Ratio: 1.5

Charge Ratio: 2

Charge Ratio: 2.5

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Specimen

Flow direction

- Span x width x height: 40 x 10 x 2 mm
- Number: 4 for each area

Stress-strain curve:

Length direction

Width direction

- Flow seems to have little effect on the destruction process of CF RTP-SMC which is considered as a brittle material

- Three-point bending tests results

- The modulus and strength in length directions has a tendency to increase and tend to decrease in width direction

- Analysis of the fiber orientation by X-ray
Method of samplings and analyze

- Analysis of the fiber orientation by X-ray
FOD results

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• Method and model
beam-solid coupling method model simplification

Use the beam-solid coupling method to create LS-DYNA models for analysis

1. Hayashi S. New simulation technology for compression molding of long fiber reinforced plastics: Application to randomly-oriented strand thermoplastic composites. ECCM 2018 - 18th European Conference on Composite Materials, 2020, p. 24–8.
2. Hayashi S., Japan Patent 6584708

- Method and model
FE model and simulation results

• Simulation correlation on FOD

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Correlation and tasks

- Area difference and edge effect

Fiber of edge part in simulation

FOD of different area

Conclusions

- **Mechanical test & Internal structure characterization**
 - ✓ Found that for one direction flow molding, as the degree of flow increases, the material modulus will be enhanced in the direction of flow, while in the direction perpendicular to the material flow, the modulus will decrease.
 - ✓ The internal structure of flowing CFRTP-SMC was studied by X-ray, and the change of fiber orientation was found.

- **Numerical simulation**
 - ✓ CFRTP-SMC material flow molding simulation was realized and verified through a FEM simulation method.
 - ✓ The fiber orientation distribution has been simulated based on different charge ratios

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Appendix

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Appendix

Material parameters in simulation

Property	Value	Unit
Resin		
Young's Modulus	0.2	MPa
Mass Density	1e-09	ton/mm ³
Friction coefficient	0.05	-
Poisson's Ratio	0.49995	-
Yield Stress	0.0001	-
Stiffness	0.2	Mpa
Fiber		
Mass Density	1.82e-09	ton/mm ³
Young's Modulus	207	GPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.3	-
Interaction		
Resistive Force	0.05	N/mm
Start-up sliding amount	0.2	mm

Geometry model parameters

Property	Value	Unit
Strand length	19	mm
Strand width	5	mm
Fiber number in width direction	6	-
Beam length	1	mm
Strands per cluster	2	-
Cluster size	7	mm

